

SPIRO-COMPOUNDS. PART V. THE FORMATION AND TRANSFORMATION OF SPIRO-COMPOUNDS FROM 3- AND 2-METHYLCYCLOHEXANONES.

BY NEUPENDRA NATH CHATTERJEE AND GIRINDRA NATH BARPUJARI.

Spiro-compounds have been built up from methylcyclohexanone to examine, on the basis of the valency deflexion hypothesis, the nature of strain in cyclohexane ring in which *ortho* or *meta* positions are occupied by groups. β -Methylnaphthalene has been obtained as a product of dehydrogenation of 3-methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-5'-carboxylic acid.

cyclohexane, which behaves as a strained ring, becomes strainless when interlocked in the *ortho* position with a six- or a five-membered ring (cf. Rao, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1954; *ibid.*, 1930, 1162; Kandiah, *ibid.*, 1931, 952). This behaviour and isomerism arising out of *cis* and *trans* lockings of two monocyclic rings have been explained on the assumption of their existence in multiplanar forms (cf. Mohr, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1918, ii, 98, 315; *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 230; Hückel and collaborators, *Nachr. Gess. Wiss. Göttingen*, 1923, 43; *Annalen*, 1924, 441, 1; 1926, 481, 109; *Ber.*, 1925, 58, 447, 1449; 1932, 65, 2137; Hückel and Friedrich, *Annalen*, 1926, 481, 132; Kandiah, *loc. cit.*). As it has not been possible yet to isolate the two strainless forms of *cyclohexane* or its monosubstituted derivatives (Werner and Conard, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 3046; Wightman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2541) the postulate of Mohr (*loc. cit.*) that they are easily interconvertible holds good. From physical considerations based on the energy associated with angular strain in homocyclic ring it might be anticipated that *cyclohexane* ring should change from one form to the other at almost every collision. Such conversion being less expected in the di-derivatives, it has been possible to separate the strainless isomers (Qudrat-i-Khuda, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 277, 482; *Nature*, 1935, 136, 301; Goldschmidt and Grafinger, *Ber.*, 1935, 68, 279; Dey and Linstead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1063; Desai, Hunter, Khan and Sahariya, *ibid.*, 1936, 416). It appeared of interest to examine on the basis of the valency deflexion hypothesis of Thorpe and Ingold (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1080) the nature of strain in the *cyclohexane* ring with *ortho* or *meta* positions substituted by groups.

3-Methylcyclohexanone cyanohydrin reacts with the sodium salt of ethyl cyanoacetate to yield the sodium salt of ethyl 1-cyano-3-methyl-

cyclohexane-1-cyanoacetate (I), which with ethyl β -chloropropionate gives diethyl 1-cyano-3-methylcyclohexane-1- α -cyanoglutarate. On hydrolysis, the above ester yields the anhydride (II) (corresponding ester is obtained on esterification) from which the required 1-carboxy-3-methylcyclohexane-1- α -glutaric acid is obtained after treatment with alkali. The ester (III), obtained from the above acid, yields diethyl 3-methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2'-one-3':5'-dicarboxylate (IV) on treatment with sodium. It is hydrolysed by means of dilute sulphuric acid (20%) to yield 3-methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2'-one-5'-carboxylic acid (V), also obtained by effecting the ring closure according to the method of Perkin and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 128).

Similar compounds have been obtained from 2-methylcyclohexanone-cyanohydrin.

The spiro-compounds (IV) (IVa) differ in no way from the *cyclohexane* analogue with respect to their formation (Chatterjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 536). As no suitable reagent could be found which attacks the one, leaving the other intact, nothing can be said at present as regards the difference in their stability. Isolation of the strainless isomers of compounds in which the damping effect of the spiro-*cyclopentane* ring is expected, is now being tried.

Incidentally it might be mentioned that our knowledge of the ring transformation during selenium dehydrogenation is limited. An observation in this line has been made in which β -methyl-naphthalene has been produced from 3-methyl-*cyclohexane*-spiro-*cyclopentane*-5'-carboxylic acid (VI) obtained by the Clemmensen reduction of the keto acid (V).

Experiments are in progress to study the ring transformation of the spiro-compounds from 2-methyl-*cyclohexanone*.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Diethyl 1-Cyano-3-methylcyclohexane-1- α -cyanoglutarate. — 3-Methyl-*cyclohexanone* cyanohydrin was prepared in good yield as follows: 3-Methyl-*cyclohexanone* (100 g.) was shaken with a solution of sodium bisulphite (200 g.) in water (250 c.c.) and the ice-cold mixture gradually treated with a solution of potassium cyanide (80 g.) in water (150 c.c.). After 2 hours the cyanohydrin was extracted by means of ether, washed with water, and then with a saturated solution of sodium chloride, dried (anhydrous sodium sulphate), and the solvent removed with the addition of two drops of concentrated sulphuric acid. It was then distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 132-135°/20 mm. To a well cooled solution of this freshly distilled 1-hydroxy-1-cyano-3-methyl-*cyclohexane* (134 g.)

in absolute alcohol (134 c.c.), a suspension of ethyl sodiocyanoacetate, obtained from ethyl cyanoacetate (118 g.), sodium (23.3 g.) and alcohol (354 c.c.), was gradually added with vigorous shaking. The mixture after being kept at 0° for 6 hours and at room temperature for 3 days, was mixed with ethyl β -chloropropionate (160 g.) and after the initial reaction had abated, boiled under reflux until a test portion, diluted with water, was neutral to litmus (about 40 hours). The mixture was filtered, washed with dry ether and the filtrate diluted with water and extracted with ether; the ethereal extract was washed with a large volume of water to remove alcohol, dried and ether recovered. It distilled as a viscous liquid, b.p. 216°/5 mm., yield 100 g. (Found: C, 64.5; H, 7.5. $C_{18}H_{26}O_4N_2$ requires C, 64.6; H, 7.7 per cent).

Diethyl 1-Cyano-2-methylcyclohexane-1- α -cyanoglutarate.—It was obtained from freshly distilled 1-hydroxy-1-cyano-2-methylcyclohexane as described above. In a typical experiment the cyanohydrin (96 g.) in absolute alcohol (96 c.c.) was treated with the sodium salt of ethyl cyanoacetate (84 g.) and ethyl β -chloropropionate (119 g.). The ester distilled as a viscous liquid, b.p. 212°/5 mm., and solidified on standing in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid and crystallised from ethyl alcohol in colourless crystals, m.p. 61°, yield 55 g. (Found: N, 8.5. $C_{18}H_{26}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.38 per cent).

1-Carboxy-3-methylcyclohexane-1- α -glutaric Acid.—The cyano ester (100 g.) was mixed with 6 volumes of 70% sulphuric acid and boiled under reflux for 12 hours. The condenser was removed from the flask from time to time to allow the alcohol formed to escape. The solution was then diluted with water and extracted with ether and the acid thus obtained, dissolved in sodium carbonate solution. The solution was diluted, acidified and extracted with ether. After removing ether, the product was kept in a desiccator where it solidified. It was crystallised from ether, m.p. 185° (decomp.), yield 50 g. (Found: C, 57.4; H, 6.9; Equiv., 91.8. $C_{13}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 57.3; H, 7.3 per cent. Equiv., 90.67).

The crude anhydride (II) was esterified by passing alcohol vapour through a mixture of it in alcohol containing sulphuric acid. The anhydride ester obtained after working up in the usual manner was distilled in vacuum, b.p. 187°/4 mm. (Found: C, 63.73; H, 7.83. $C_{15}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 63.8; H, 7.8 per cent).

1-Carboxy-2-methylcyclohexane-1- α -glutaric acid was obtained by the hydrolysis of diethyl 1-cyano-2-methylcyclohexane-1- α -cyanoglutarate as described above, m.p. 170° (decomp.), yield 25 g. from 55 g. of the cyano ester. (Found: C, 57.68; H, 6.86. $C_{13}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 57.3; H, 7.3 per cent).

The anhydride ester boiled at $185-190^{\circ}/4$ mm. (Found: C, 63.9; H, 8.2. $C_{15}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 63.8; H, 7.8 per cent).

Triethyl 3-Methylcyclohexane-1-carboxylate-1- α -glutarate (III).—The acid (60 g.), absolute alcohol (150 c.c.), concentrated sulphuric acid (14 c.c.), 4 litres of alcohol vapourised (4 hours) gave 50 g. of the ester, b.p. $184^{\circ}/5$ mm. (Found: C, 64.09; H, 8.82. $C_{16}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 64.04; H, 8.9 per cent).

Triethyl 2-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxylate-1- α -glutarate was obtained by the alcohol vapour method. The acid (38 g.) in alcohol (100 c.c.), containing sulphuric acid (10 c.c.), gave 20 g. of the ester on passing 3 litres of alcohol during 3-4 hours, b.p. $187^{\circ}/4$ mm. (Found: C, 64.19; H, 8.63. $C_{19}H_{28}O_6$ requires C, 64.04; H, 8.9 per cent).

Diethyl 3-methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2'-one-3':5'-dicarboxylate (IV).—A mixture of the foregoing ester (20 g.) and molecular sodium (2.3 g.) and dry benzene (50 c.c.) was refluxed for 10 minutes to start the reaction. The heating was discontinued until the vigour of the reaction abated and was then continued for 2 hours. After cooling, the product was treated with cold dilute sulphuric acid and the benzene layer was washed with aqueous sodium carbonate and with water, dried and evaporated. The residue in alcoholic solution gave a violet colouration with ferric chloride. The ester was obtained as a viscous oil (9 g.), b.p. $185-90^{\circ}/5$ mm. (Found: C, 65.92; H, 8.15. $C_{17}H_{26}O_5$ requires C, 65.8; H, 8.3 per cent).

Diethyl 2-methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2'-one-3':5'-dicarboxylate (IVa) was obtained by the above method. In a typical experiment the ester (12 g.) was subjected to the action of molecular sodium (1.4 g.) in dry benzene (40 c.c.), b.p. $180-185^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 5 g. (Found: C, 66.2; H, 8.4. $C_{17}H_{26}O_5$ requires C, 65.8; H, 8.3 per cent). It gave deep violet colouration with ferric chloride.

3-Methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2'-one-5'-carboxylic Acid (V).—The ester was refluxed with excess of dilute sulphuric acid (20%) for 12 hours and the cooled solution saturated with ammonium sulphate and repeatedly extracted with ether, the extract washed with water and dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removing the ether it was kept in a desiccator where it solidified into a crystalline mass, m.p. $140-43^{\circ}$ (after previous softening). (Found: C, 68.69; H, 8.31; $E_{\text{equiv.}}$, 209. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 68.5; H, 8.5 per cent. $E_{\text{equiv.}}$, 210).

3-Methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2-one-5'-carboxylic Acid (V).—This acid was also formed when the sodium salt of 1-carboxy-3-methyl-

cyclohexane-1-a-glutaric acid was heated with acetic anhydride. The dry sodium salt (9 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) were mixed in a 100 c.c. flask fitted with a condenser. The flask was gradually heated in an oil-bath which was maintained at 130-140° for about 8 hours when the evolution of carbon dioxide was almost over. After removing most of the acetic anhydride under reduced pressure, absolute ethyl alcohol (50 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) were added, and the mixture heated for 8 hours. After dilution with water, the separated oil was extracted with ether, washed with sodium bicarbonate, dried and the ether removed. It was then heated on a water-bath with aqueous alcoholic caustic soda. After dilution, alcohol was removed and the solution acidified. The gummy mass, which separated, was extracted with ether. After removing ether, the product was kept in a vacuum desiccator, when it solidified, m.p. 140-43° (with previous softening). (Found: C, 68·7; H, 8·4. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 68·5; H, 8·5 per cent).

Ethyl 3-methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2'-one-5'-carboxylate, prepared by refluxing a solution of the keto-acid (5 g.) in absolute alcohol (20 c.c.) with the addition of absolute alcohol (5 c.c.), saturated at 0° with hydrogen chloride, formed a colourless viscous oil, b. p. 135-140°/4 mm.

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 185° after previous softening. (Found: N, 13·8. $C_{15}H_{25}O_3N_3$ requires N, 14·2 per cent).

Ethyl 2-Methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2'-one-5'-carboxylate.—The ester (IV) was refluxed with excess of dilute sulphuric acid (20%) for 12 hours and the cooled solution saturated with ammonium sulphate and extracted with ether. On removing ether the keto-acid was obtained as a gum. It was further hydrolysed with alcoholic caustic soda and after working up in the usual manner, was esterified by refluxing (6 hours) a solution of this keto-acid in absolute alcohol, saturated at 0° with hydrogen chloride, b.p. 142-148°/6 mm. (Found: C, 70·7; H, 9·2. $C_{14}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 70·5; H, 9·2 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 202°. (Found: N, 14·45. $C_{15}H_{25}O_3N_3$ requires N, 14·24 per cent).

3-Methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-5'-carboxylic Acid (VI).—The pure keto-acid (V) (7 g.), amalgamated zinc (45 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (60 c.c.) were refluxed for 12 hours, further quantity of the acid (30 c.c.) was then added and the heating continued for 12 hours. The solution was extracted with ether, and the extract dried with anhydrous

sodium sulphate. After removing the solvent it was kept in a vacuum desiccator when it solidified. It was crystallised from ether, m.p. 62-65° (with previous softening). (Found: C, 73.0; H, 9.93. $C_{12}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 73.4; H, 10.2 per cent).

β-Methylnaphthalene. — 3-Methylcyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-5'-carboxylic acid (7 g.) and selenium (25 g.) were heated at 280-90° for 20 hours. and then at 330° for 30 hours. The reaction product was extracted with ether. After removing ether, the residue was distilled over sodium in vacuum. A small quantity of a liquid was collected and converted into picrate, m.p. 115° (mixed m.p. with a genuine sample of the picrate of 3-methyl-naphthalene).

Our respectful thanks are due to Sir P. C. Rây and Dr. P. C. Mitter for their kind interest in the work.

SIR P. C. RAY FELLOW'S LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
& TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

Received September 28, 1938.
